

INCIDENCE OF CHEMOTHERAPY-INDUCED PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY IN ONCOLOGY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) is a common and potentially debilitating side effect of several chemotherapeutic agents, including taxanes, platinum compounds, and vinca alkaloids. CIPN significantly impacts patients' quality of life, treatment adherence, and long-term functional outcomes.

Objective: This study aims to assess the incidence of CIPN in oncology patients undergoing chemotherapy and identify associated risk factors such as age, type of chemotherapy, cumulative dose, and pre-existing conditions.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on oncology patients receiving chemotherapy at a tertiary care center over a 12-month period. CIPN was assessed using standardized clinical tools and patient-reported outcome measures at baseline and during each treatment cycle.

Results: Out of 166 patients enrolled, 37% developed CIPN, with the highest incidence observed among those receiving paclitaxel and oxaliplatin. Older age and higher cumulative doses were significantly associated with increased risk. Most cases presented with sensory symptoms, while a smaller proportion exhibited motor and autonomic involvement.

Conclusion: CIPN remains a prevalent and under-recognized complication in cancer care. Early identification and regular monitoring are essential to mitigate long-term disability. These findings underscore the need for tailored preventive and management strategies in high-risk populations.

Keywords: Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy, CIPN, Oncology, Cancer patients, Neurotoxicity, Chemotherapy side effects, Paclitaxel, Oxaliplatin, Incidence, Quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Despite much advances in the field of medicine and technology, cancer is still a scary word and almost everyone knows that they get very sick or die from cancer. Cancer is a very fatal disease with high incidence that threatens health and family in society. Cancer is defined as a disease in which a group of abnormal cells grown uncontrollably by ignoring the normal rules of cell division.

Normal cells subjected to signals that dictate whether the cells should divide, differentiate in to another cell or die. These cells develop a degree of autonomy from these signals results in uncontrolled proliferation .If this proliferation continues and spread, it can be fatal. Almost all cancer related deaths are due to tumor spreading which is known as metastasis.Cancer as a disease involves changes in cell genome that produce proteins that disrupt the cellular balance between cell division and quiescence, resulting in continuous cell division that form cancers.

TYPES OF CANCER:

The term cancer comprises more than 100 diseases affecting nearly every part of the body.A tumor can be either benign(often it is harmless, neither invading nor spreading to other body sites) or malignant(results in metastasis).Pathologically, cancers are classified into three categories which are mentioned below:

Carcinoma: It is the most common type of cancer that starts in the cells that make up the skin and tissue lining organs such as liver and kidneys. It occurs many parts of the body and some common types of carcinoma includes: squamous cell carcinoma, renal cell carcinoma, ductal carcinoma in situ, invasive ductal carcinoma.

Sarcoma: It is a rare kind of cancer which is different from much more form of carcinomas, because they occur in a different kind of tissues like connective tissues and these type of tumors are most common in bones, muscles, tendons, cartilage, nerves, fat and blood vessels of arms and legs.

Lymphoma and Leukemia: Lymphoma is a cancer that occurs in the cells of the immune system. various types of lymphomas are T-cell lymphoma, B-cell lymphoma, hodgkin lymphoma, non-hodgkin lymphoma and lymphoproliferative lymphomas. Leukemia is a blood cancer caused by increased number of immature or abnormal

leucocytes. The major types of leukemia are acute lymphocytic leukemia(ALL),acute myelogenous leukemia(AML), chronic lymphatic leukemia(CLL),chronic myelogenous leukemia(CML).

CARCINOGENESIS: ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS OF CANCER

Carcinogenesis or oncogenesis or tumorigenesis means mechanism of induction of tumours. Agents which can induce tumours are called carcinogens. Initiation and progression of cancer depends on external factors (tobacco, chemicals, radiation and infectious organisms) as well as internal factors(mutations that occur from metabolism and inheritance, hormones, immune conditions).

Risk of cancers are also increased by infectious agents including HBV,HPV,HIV and bacteria such as H.pylori(stomach cancers).Although cancer can occur in all age group persons, it is common among in elderly which is above 65 years. The incidence of some of the cancers such as breast, colorectal, prostate, lung increases with age.

Pathogenesis of cancer can be viewed as multi step process

involving four main steps as follows:

1)Mutation and tumour initiation

Genetic alteration leads to mutation in a single cell that results in tumour cell formation by abnormal proliferation.

2)Cell proliferation and tumour progression

As the tumour progression continues, additional mutations occurs within the tumour cells.These additional mutations become dominant within tumour cell and shows rapid growth and division.

3)Clonal selection and malignancy

Tumour cell proliferation leads to new clone of tumour cells with rapid growth and certain properties like invasion,survival and metastasis. This process is known as clonal selection. If these clonal selection continues throughout tumour development,the tumour grows rapidly and malignancy will be increased.

4)Metastasis:

Metastasis is a process in which tumour cells migrate and spread the cancer to different sites from where they originated. The stages of metastasis are: local invasion, intravasation, transport, extravasation, formation of micrometastasis, colonisation.

CANCER TREATMENT:

Early advances ensures that the cancer can be controlled. some of the treatments as mentioned below may control cancers.

1.RADIATION 2.SURGERY 3.CHEMOTHERAPY 4.HORMONE THERAPY
5.STEM CELL TRANSPLANT 6.TARGET THERAPY

CHEMOTHERAPY OF CANCER:

The National Cancer Institute defines chemotherapy as drugs that treat cancer cells. Chemotherapy kills cancer cells by damaging DNA, interrupts with DNA synthesis or inhibiting cell division. Unlike radiation and surgery, which targets specific areas, chemo can work throughout the body. Most chemotherapy agents target rapidly proliferating cells, like those of skin, hair, intestine and bone marrow ,that's why side effects like alopecia, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting and bone marrow depression occurs frequently while taking chemotherapy.

Chemotherapy can be given by various routes such as intra-arterial, intraperitoneal, intrathecal, intravenous, topical and oral route.

GOALS OF CHEMOTHERAPY:

The goals of chemotherapy may vary from each person's situation and there are three main goals for chemotherapy in cancer treatment:

1)CURE: In most cases, the treatment can destroy cancer cells means when possible, chemo is used to eliminate cancer cells until they are no longer detected in the body.

2)CONTROL: If a cure is not possible in various cancers, in that case the goal of the cancer treatment is to control the disease by slows its growth or destroy cancer cells that have spread to other parts of the body.

3)PALLIATION: It means to ease the symptoms caused by the cancer, when cancer is in the advanced stage, the goal of chemotherapy is to improve the quality of life by palliative treatment. In certain cases chemo may be used to shrink tumors that are causing pain or pressure. Chemo given after surgery or radiation is called adjuvant therapy. Adjuvant therapy is given to kill any cancer cells left in the body after surgery. chemo given before surgery is called as neoadjuvant therapy to shrink the tumor to make it easier to be removed surgically.

CHEMOTHERAPY INDUCED PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY (CIPN)

CIPN is a common progressive adverse effect of many chemotherapy agents After chemotherapy, approximately 70% of cancer patients have painful neuropathy at 6 months improving to around 35% at 1year.Eventhough different chemotherapies have variable characteristics, but symptoms tend to be predominantly sensory. Sensory toxicity is the predominant feature consists of positive and negative symptoms. Positive symptoms are paresthesia, dysaesthesia, cold and mechanical hypersensitivity. Negative symptoms include numbness, loss of vibration sense, proprioception and deep tendon reflexes.

Chemotherapy induced peripheral neuropathy is caused by many of the most commonly used chemotherapy agents including taxanes (paclitaxel ,docetaxel), platinum compounds (oxaliplatin, cisplatin), vinca alkaloids (vincristine) and protease inhibitors (bortezomib), immunomodulatory agents(thalidomide).

The mechanism by which neurotoxic chemotherapeutic agents can damage the nervous system structures and cause CIPN involves microtubule disruption, oxidative stress, mitochondrial damage, altered ion channel activity, myelin sheath damage, DNA damage, immunological processes and neuroinflammation

A number of predisposing risk factors of CIPN have been identified, those factors includes patient age, gender, co-morbidities like diabetes, a history of smoking, impaired renal function and exposure to other neurotoxic chemotherapeutic agents. Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) identified some single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with higher risk of CIPN. The reported

polymorphisms are associated with a range of proteins, including voltage-gated sodium channels, Schwann cell function related proteins, receptors for cell surface collagen, receptors involved in neuronal apoptosis, neuronal crest cell development and an enzyme involved in pyruvate metabolism. Another well recognized major risk factor of CIPN is the cumulative dose of chemotherapeutic agents.

Common sites of involvement by neurotoxic drug classification

Agent	Sites of peripheral nerve damage
Cisplatin	Dorsal root ganglion
Oxaliplatin	Dorsal root ganglion; ion channels
Paclitaxel	Dorsal root ganglion; microtubules; nerve terminals
Docetaxel	Dorsal root ganglion; microtubules; mitochondria; nerve terminals

Bortezomib	Microtubules; mitochondrial and endoplasmic reticulum; dysregulation of neurotrophins
Vincristine	Dorsal root ganglion; microtubules; nerve terminals

DRUG-SPECIFIC CLINICAL PRESENTATIONS AND NEUROTOXICITY IN CIPN

Platinum compounds:

The parent compound, cisplatin, has been in widespread use for forty years. It commonly causes ototoxicity with hearing loss and tinnitus, sensory neuropathy, nephropathy and myelosuppression. The latter two adverse events are manageable by pre-hydration of patients with normal saline or bone marrow stimulating agents (erythropoietin and G-CSF). The neuropathy and ototoxicity are only preventable with dose reduction or cessation of drug. Significant, dose-related moderate or severe hearing loss (20%) and tinnitus (40%) are reported in patients treated with cisplatin. It is often permanent . Since both CIPN and hearing loss are dose-related, they occur concurrently in many patients but there is not a clear mechanistic or risk-based relationship between these effects. All of the platinum agents in routine use cause long-term peripheral sensory damage, much of which is due to neuronopathy . This occurs in 30–40% of patients treated with oxaliplatin and cisplatin and in the same proportion of patients treated with the commonly used combination of paclitaxel and carboplatin . Of the platinum compounds cisplatin seems to be most frequently involved in peripheral neurotoxicity . Carboplatin is considered as less neurotoxic than cisplatin . Treatment schedules and formulations can influence toxicity. In addition to the chronic neurotoxicities observed in all platinum-based compounds , oxaliplatin is frequently associated with transient acute effects. Oxaliplatin acute

neuropathic pain typically involves cold-induced dysesthesia that are most severe in the hands, face, and oral cavity. Cold wind on the face or cold drinks may induce intense pain. The symptoms typically begin with the second or third cycle of treatment and last for 2–4 days after druginfusion.

An important characteristic of platinum-based CIPN is the so-called “coasting” phenomenon. This refers to the observation that CIPN from platinum-based (especially cisplatin and oxaliplatin) agents may worsen for several months following the discontinuation of therapy. Coasting is disturbing for both the patient and the physician, who are expecting stabilization or improvement of neuropathic symptoms after the chemotherapy is stopped. Much of the basic research into platinum-based CIPN pathomechanisms has focused on neurotoxic damage to dorsal root ganglion sensory neurons . Platinum-based compounds (cisplatin, oxaliplatin, carboplatin and analogs) damage dorsal root ganglia neurons by forming adducts with nuclear and mitochondrial DNA. Animal studies have shown that this leads to neuronal apoptosis due to aberrant entry into the cell cycle , which corresponds to the clinical pattern of a neuronopathy. There is also direct damage to mitochondria due to impairment of mitochondrial DNA transcription, which has been theorized to underlie “coasting” . Platinum adducts with nuclear DNA are repaired by nucleotide excision repair. This DNA repair process is not present in mitochondria. The accumulated and unrepaired Pt-DNA adducts in mitochondria may then lead to gradual attrition of intrinsic mitochondrial proteins due to failure of transcription after cessation of drug therapy. The acute symptoms of cold-induced dysesthesia in the hands and mouth from oxaliplatin are likely due to its effect on voltage-gated sodium channel kinetics . This acute neurotoxicity is temporally independent of cumulative sensory toxicity but there is a correlation between the severity of dysesthesiae and the likelihood of developing the fixed sensory neuropathy.

Platinum compounds (cisplatin/ carboplatin/oxaliplatin)

Pathogenesis :-

Dorsal root ganglion represent the main structure that is affected by the deposition of platinum compounds, thereby generating neurotoxicity. 59 Two putative mechanisms are primarily involved in platinum-induced neurotoxicity, and DRG neuron apoptosis is the common cornerstone. Firstly, they are able to alter the tertiary structure of DNA by forming intrastrand adducts and interstrand crosslinks. Moreover, it has been

documented that the neuronal apoptosis on DRG could be triggered by oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction with a release of the cytochrome-c pathway, independence of Fas receptor activation, or by increased activity of p53, p38, and ERK1/2. The pathogenesis of oxaliplatin-induced neurotoxicity does not share the same characteristics, as this platinum compound induces two clinically distinct forms of neurotoxicity, namely acute and chronic. The chronic, sensory form is considered to be induced by the morphologic and functional changes in the DRG cells, resulting from the local deposition and accumulation of oxaliplatin. On the other hand, the acute form is thought to be caused by a dysfunction of nodal axonal voltage-gated Na⁺ channels, likely resulting from the oxalate chelating effect on both Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ incidence, severity, and risk factors. The combination of cisplatin/ paclitaxel exerts additive effects in producing neuropathy at higher rates than cisplatin monotherapy. Available data show that carboplatin is almost unrelated to peripheral neuropathy when given as monotherapy at an area under the curve of 6 (AUC₆), while its administration at an AUC₁₂ is not associated with the occurrence of grade 3–4 neurotoxicity. As such, carboplatin is definitely much less neurotoxic than cisplatin or oxaliplatin. As to the acute form of neurotoxicity induced by oxaliplatin, it is generally acknowledged that the vast majority of patients treated with various oxaliplatin-based regimens at a dose ranging from 85–130 mg/m² experience some grade of neurotoxicity. Severe acute oxaliplatin induced peripheral neuropathy that requires prolongation of oxaliplatin infusion or treatment discontinuation may occur in up to 22% of treated patients.⁷⁵ Cold temperatures and the time of oxaliplatin infusion are the main risk factors of acute OXLI PN. On the other hand, the overall rate of neurosensory symptoms in the context of chronic oxaliplatin-induced neurotoxicity can range from 60%–75% in patients assigned to be treated with oxaliplatin-based regimens, including Data from large studies show that treatment-emergent grade 3–4 neurotoxicity can occur in up to 20% of oxaliplatin-treated patients, but it can be predicted by clinical and neurophysiological information obtained at mid-treatment. The cumulative oxaliplatin dose, time of infusion, and the existence of peripheral neuropathy prior to the initiation of chemotherapy rank among the most important triggers of chronic OXAI PN genesis. In addition to these well-known risk factors, recent evidence from a large homogeneous series of colorectal cancer patients showed that patients who have a more complex combination of acute phenomena related to axonal hyperexcitability are those who eventually develop more

severe chronic neurotoxicity. Furthermore, it seems that the chemotherapy regimen may also represent a risk factor of OXAIPN. This view was supported by a recently Advanced age does not seem to represent a significant risk factor of OXAIPN in patients without any other significant comorbidity

Clinical and electrophysiological characteristics:-

The clinical spectrum of cisplatin-induced peripheral neuropathy is comprised of sensory symptoms in a stocking-and-glove distribution, decreased vibration, and proprioception and suppression or loss of DTRs. Neurophysiology is in keeping with an axonal sensory peripheral neuropathy with a decrease or abolishment of sensory action potentials and normal sensory conduction velocities. Signs and symptoms of acute OXLI PN may begin during the infusion or within 1–2 days of oxaliplatin administration and mostly include distal and perioral cold-induced paresthesias and dysesthesias. However, other uncommon symptoms, such as shortness of breath, jaw spasm, fasciculations, cramps, and difficulty swallowing may also be present at significant rates. Voice and visual changes, ptosis, and pseudo-laryngospasm rarely occur. Recording of repetitive compound action potentials, high-frequency discharges of motor unit multiplets, and bursts of muscle fiber action potentials are evident during nerve conduction study and needle electromyography examination. This pattern is in keeping with neuromyotonia as a result of excessive nerve excitability, distally attenuated. The clinical and neurophysiological characteristics of chronic OXLI PN are generally similar to those of cisplatin.

Long term outcomes

Although there are few specifically designed studies to assess the long-term course of platinum-induced neurotoxicity, it is expected to improve or completely resolve within 1 year after the discontinuation of treatment. However, there have been cases in which CIPN remained persistent or at best, partially reversible, because of the “coasting” phenomenon resulting from the capacity of platinum compounds to accumulate in DRG for a long time.

Options for treatment or prevention Based on results from randomized controlled trials (RCTs), there are no effective symptomatic treatments, and only duloxetine at a dose of 60 mg per day has been shown in a well-designed RCT to be effective in alleviating oxaliplatin-associated neuropathic pain. As to prophylaxis, there have been

insufficient data thus far, to support the use of any candidate chemoprotective agents, such as acetylcysteine, amifostine, calcium and magnesium, or vitamin E to prevent or limit the neurotoxicity of platinum compounds. As such, adherence to the non-pharmacological stop-and-go approach (ie, intermittent oxaliplatin dosing) may be warranted to prevent platinum compound-induced peripheral neuropathy.

Anti-Microtubule agents :

Taxanes:- Taxanes (paclitaxel, docetaxel,) are widely used in oncology, and typically cause a dose-dependent, painful, length-dependent, sensory neuropathy due to dying back axonopathy. It may be partially reversible after treatment is discontinued.. Additionally, an acute, transient pain syndrome occurs in over half of patients treated with paclitaxel. It is characterized primarily by aching musculoskeletal pain. This syndrome is not clearly due to nerve damage; however, it shares many clinical features with CIPN and may correlate with the development of paclitaxel-induced CIPN.

Taxanes stabilize the dynamic assembly of polymer microtubule subunits. While they are thought to primarily exert their cancer-killing effects via disruption of microtubule-mediated cell division, it is less clear how they cause CIPN. Microtubules serve as the track for axonal transport, and taxanes interrupt this *in vitro*, which may lead to neuropathy. In other form of damage to mitochondria that may underlie a metabolic axonal failure in CIPN.

New anti-microtubule agents :- Over the past several years, new chemotherapy agents have come to market that also impact microtubule dynamics. Eribulin and ixabepilone are two drugs used to treat breast cancer and cause an axonal sensorimotor peripheral neuropathy. These drugs bind to the same site and have the same effect on microtubule dynamics as the taxanes. A new pharmaceutical approach is the conjugation of a chemotherapy agent with tumor specific antibodies as used in brentuximab vedotin where an antibody to CD30 (present on lymphoma) is conjugated to a microtubule toxin (monomethyl auristatin E). Despite the targeting to lymphoma, brentuximab vedotin causes an off-target peripheral neuropathy in 30–50% of patients. Ado-trastuzumab emtansine combines an antibody against HER2 (breast cancer) and emtansine, which inhibits

assembly of microtubule polymers and is associated with a high frequency of peripheral neuropathy.

Pathogenesis

Conventionally, the mechanisms underlying the pathogenesis of taxane-induced peripheral neuropathy (TIPN) include interference with microtubule-based axonal transport, macrophage activation in both the DRG and peripheral nerve, as well as microglial activation within the spinal cord. As a result of the problematic signal transduction, there is evidence of a “dying back” process starting from the distal nerve endings followed by effects on Schwann cells and Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy neuronal bodies, or disturbed axonal transport changes in the affected neurons. Recent evidence shows that the activation of spinal astrocytes and the inhibition of microtubule-based fast axonal transport may also be significant contributors to TIPN.²¹ The structure of internodal myelin in peripheral nerves remains unaffected in TIPN.²² incidence, severity, and risk factors Paclitaxel appears to be more neurotoxic than docetaxel with an overall incidence of about 60% and 15% for each agent, respectively. Current evidence shows that the most important triggering factor of TIPN is the accumulation of doses over the course of chemotherapy with a neurotoxic threshold of 1,000 mg/m² for paclitaxel and 400 mg/m² for docetaxel Grade 3–4 sensory neuropathy is much more common with paclitaxel than with docetaxel. The nanoparticle albumin-bound (Nab) form of paclitaxel was formulated to enable lower doses and reduce toxicity, but clinical experience shows that grade 2 peripheral neuropathy still remains a significant treatment-limiting toxicity. Other risk factors include prior or concomitant administration of platinum compounds, pre-existing peripheral neuropathy due to

various medical conditions, and duration of infusion The issue relating to the risk of neurotoxicity after the administration of weekly versus every 3 weeks paclitaxel treatment schedules has been conflictingly addressed. There was evidence to suggest that the risk is lower with the weekly paclitaxel schedule, while the opposite was demonstrated in other studies. The risk appears to be unrelated to advanced age.

Clinical and electrophysiological characteristics:-

Usually, patients affected by TIPN complain of paresthesia, numbness, and/or neuropathic pain in a stocking-and glove distribution. Clinical examination documents loss of proprioception and suppression or loss of deep tendon reflexes (DTRs). Nerve conduction studies reveal the decrease or abolishment of sensory responses in keeping with an axonal sensory neuropathy as a result of axonal loss from sensory nerves. The sural nerve is particularly affected. Motor involvement with reduction of compound muscle action potential responses and myopathy with proximal weakness is less frequently seen. The significance of sympathetic skin response to provide electrophysiological evidence of small fiber neuropathy in taxane-treated patients merits further study course of neurotoxicity Symptoms usually improve or resolve within 3 months after the discontinuation of treatment, whereas severe symptoms may persist for a longer period.

Proteasome inhibitors

Bortezomib exerts its anti-neoplastic actions by inhibiting proteasomes, the primary intracellular protein degradation machinery. Bortezomib causes a painful length-dependent small fiber predominant axonal sensory neuropathy. It is a reversible distal axonopathy. Recently it was discovered that subcutaneous delivery decreases the likelihood and severity of the neuropathy. A small proportion of patients receiving bortezomib develop a severe polyradiculoneuropathy, which appears to be immune-mediated Newer generation proteasome inhibitors, carfilzomib and ixazomib, are reported to have a lower incidence of CIPN. Interestingly, despite the potential widespread cellular impact of proteasome inhibition, bortezomib appears to be neurotoxic due to interference with microtubule and mitochondrial function. Bortezomib increases microtubule polymerization and mitochondrial exhibit decreased axonal transport and function in sensory neurons but the precise mechanism of how this occurs is unclear. Other mechanisms may also be important in bortezomib induced peripheral neuropathy, including nuclear accumulations of ubiquitinated proteins and altered protein transcription in sensory ganglion neurons

Pathogenesis:-

The pathogenetic hallmark of bortezomib-induced peripheral neuropathy (BIPN) consists of morphological alterations in the spinal cord, DRG, and peripheral nerves with specific functional alterations in A δ and C peripheral nerve fibers. In addition, proteasome inhibition, increased α -tubulin polymerization, mitochondrial and endoplasmic reticulum damage, and dysregulation of neurotrophins through inhibition of NF κ B activation may also significantly contribute to BIPN genesis. incidence, severity, and risk factors

The incidence of clinically significant, ie, grade 1–2 BIPN, can occur in up to 75% patients with multiple myeloma who have relapsed after or were refractory to frontline therapy, while treatment emergent grade 3–4 neurotoxicity may appear in 12% of bortezomib-treated patients.^{100,101} BIPN is usually exacerbated in patients with pre-existing neuropathy and comorbidities associated with peripheral nerve damage. However, the cumulative dose effect of bortezomib remains the main triggering factor of BIPN, although the severity of neurotoxicity is escalated until the completion of the first five cycles of bortezomib administration and thereafter remains stable. Bortezomib administered subcutaneously rather than intravenously has an improved safety profile and appears to be ideal for patients with pre-existing neuropathy or at a high risk of developing neurotoxicity.

Clinical and electrophysiological characteristics

The cardinal symptom of BIPN is neuropathic pain and paresthesias in distal extremities of limbs, in keeping with a painful neuropathy due to dysfunction in all three major fiber (A β , A δ , and C) types of sensory nerves, as demonstrated in both clinical and animal models.^{95,105} Neurological examination reveals distal sensory loss to all modalities and changes in proprioception, while DTRs are either suppressed or absent. Nerve conduction study usually reveals typical findings of CIPN consistent with a distal, sensory, axonal neuronopathy.

Motor involvement is occasionally present. Reversal of BIPN usually occurs after a median interval of 3 months following the discontinuation of bortezomib treatment, but it may persist for up to 2 years or remain indefinitely in some cases. Options for treatment or prevention Lafutidine, a H₂-blocker with gastroprotective activity, may be able to prevent or improve BIPN, based on the results of a

recently published small case series of eight patients. However, the protective activity of lafutidine against BIPN needs to be further demonstrated in large RCTs. As such, there is no proven effective prophylactic treatment to prevent the development of BIPN, and medication towards this aspect is merely symptomatic.⁹⁸ Therefore, likewise to the case of EIPN, adherence to the dose modification guidelines is advised.

Other drugs less commonly associated with CIPN

Fluorouracil or 5-FU is a pyrimidine analog, and peripheral neuropathy associated with its administration is unusual. Anyhow, the literature contains a small series of two patients experiencing neurotoxicity while they were receiving chemotherapy with 5-FU.¹¹⁴ Gemcitabine may occasionally evoke peripheral neuropathy with paresthesia's and myalgias, whereas neurotoxicity rarely occurs while patients are treated with methotrexate, cytosine arabinoside (Ara-C), or topoisomerase inhibitors, such as irinotecan or topotecan.

Type of neuropathy and clinical pattern of CiPN by neurotoxic drug classification

Agent	Type of neuropathy	Clinical pattern
Cisplatin	Sensory	Paresthesia, numbness in a stocking-and-glove distribution
Oxaliplatin	Chronic sensory; acute transient neuropathy	Paresthesia, numbness and/or neuropathic pain in a stocking and-glove distribution; neuromyotonia-like symptoms
Paclitaxel	Sensory; occasionally sensorimotor	Paresthesia, numbness and/or neuropathic pain in a stocking

		and-glove distribution; myalgia, myopathy
Docetaxel	Sensory; occasionally sensorimotor	Same as paclitaxel
Bortezomib	Painful sensory	Neuropathic pain and paresthesias in distal extremities of limbs
vincristine	Sensorimotor; autonomic; cranial nerves	Paresthesia, numbness and/or neuropathic pain in a stocking and-glove distribution; muscle cramps, mild distal weakness

STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN PERIPHERAL NERVES

Cancer chemotherapy agents may differentially affect specific peripheral nervous system (PNS) structures to produce neuronopathy, axonopathy and/or myelinopathy that contribute to the pathogenesis of painful CIPN. Cancer chemotherapy-induced peripheral nerve injury appears to be due primarily to axonopathy that is seen both in patients with CIPN. Thus, peripheral nerve degeneration or small fiber neuropathy is generally accepted as underpinning the development of CIPN.

THE LONGEST AXONS ARE THE FIRST AFFECTED

Peripheral nerves contain a variety of nerve fibers that differ in their respective morphology, degree of myelination, function and biochemical features. These various fiber types are differentially sensitive to the neurotoxic effects of cancer chemotherapy agents with the longest nerves having the greatest vulnerability. This may be related to their higher metabolic requirements. Clinically, symptoms develop initially in the feet and hands, followed by proximal progression to the ankles and wrists in a “stocking and glove” distribution.

METHODOLOGY

Study site: Both In patient ward & Out patient Department of Oncology, Tertiary Care hospital

Study Duration: Six months

Sample size: 166 cases

Study Design: Prospective observational study

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with oncologic disease under potential neurotoxic chemotherapy
- Patients of both Genders.
- Patients with all type of cancers
- Patients of both diabetic and non diabetic were included.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with multiple co-morbidities.
- Patients who are not under potential neurotoxic chemotherapy
- Patients with traumatic injuries.
- Patients with metabolic problems.

Source of data collection:

- Case sheet received from Cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy.
- Direct interaction with Patient/Patient’s representatives.

Method of data collection:

- Patient demographics like age, gender, type of cancer, Type of chemotherapy, patient’s co-morbidities, grading of neuropathy etc. were collected in a specially designed data collection form.

- Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) is widely accepted throughout the oncology community as the standard classification and severity grading scale for adverse events in cancer therapy and other oncology settings. The National Cancer Institute issued the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE). These measures rely upon patient self-reporting which consists of five graded scores which are the weighted sums of the questions in their section. Each grade varies with both motor and sensory symptoms. The higher the grade the greater disability i.e., a grade of grade 4 will be the maximum disability and a grade of 1 is equivalent to asymptomatic level.
- Five grades includes physical functioning, Activities of daily living The Instrumental ADL refer to preparing meals, shopping for groceries or clothes, using the telephone, managing money. Self-care ADL refers to bathing, dressing/undressing, feeding self, using the toilet, taking medications, and not bedridden and role limitations due to effects of chemotherapy, and general health perceptions.

The above said scale were tabulated in a data collection form to make the final interpretation easier.

Study Instrument:

The Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) consists of five graded scores, which are the weighted sums of the questions in their section. Each grade varies with both motor and sensory symptoms. The higher the grade the greater disability i.e., a grade of grade 4 will be the maximum disability and a grade of 1 is equivalent to asymptomatic level.

The Five grades are:

Motor	Sensory
• Asymptomatic.	Asymptomatic.
• Instrumental ADL is limited.	Deep tendon reflex or paraesthesia loss.
• Limiting self care ADL	Limiting self care ADL
• Life threatning	Life threatning
• Death	Death

Uses:

- Evaluating individual patients neuropathy level
- Identifying the prevalence of neuropathy in use of neurotoxic chemotherapy
- Monitoring and comparing the range of disability in patients

Limitations:

- This study does not take into consideration other than drugs causing neurotoxicity
- This study does not include the multiple co-morbidities associated with neuropathy

Data analysis :

Data was analyzed by using (Excel) Microsoft corporation 2013.

Ethical committee clearance:

Institutional ethical committee approved our study. It doesn't involve any administration of drugs to humans or animals and as there is no collection of specimen or serum samples, informed consent form was collected from the patients to collect the data.

RESULTS**Table-1: Socio-Demographic&Clinical Characteristics of cancer patients**

S.No	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Gender		
	Male	41	25.0
	Female	125	75.0
2.	Age		
	23-40	20	12.05
	40-80	146	87.95
3.	Diabetes		
	Yes	6	100
	No	0	0
4.	Drugs		
	Paclitaxel	63	38%
	Cisplatin	23	14%
	Docetaxel	12	7%
	Oxaliplatin	11	7%
	Carboplatin	2	1%
	Bortezomib	1	0.60%

Characteristics	CIPN(+) (n=112)	CIPN(-) (n=54)
Age		
Sex		
Male	25	17
Female	87	37

Type of cancer		
BREAST	41 (36.60%)	16 (29.62%)
BUCCAL MUCOSA	4 (3.57%)	1 (1.85%)
CERVIX	14 (12.50%)	9 (16.66%)
ENDOMETRIUM	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
EPIGLOTTIS	0	1 (1.85%)
GASTROESOPHAGEAL JUNCTION	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
GINGIVA	0	1 (1.85%)
HARD PALATE	1 (0.89%)	1 (1.85%)
HYPOPHARYNX	1 (0.89%)	1 (1.85%)
LARYNX	1 (0.89%)	2 (3.70%)
LUNG	6 (5.35%)	3 (5.55%)
NASOPHARYNX	0	1 (1.85%)
OVARY	11 (9.82%)	2 (3.70%)
PANCREAS	1 (0.89%)	2 (3.70%)
POST CROCICOID	2 (1.78%)	2 (3.70%)
RECTOSIGMOID	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
RETROMOLAR TRIGONE	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
STOMACH	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
TONGUE	5 (4.46%)	1 (1.85%)
UPPER ESOPHAGUS	2 (1.78%)	1 (1.85%)
VULVA	1 (0.89%)	1 (1.85%)
GASTRIC CANCER	0	1 (1.85%)
PENIS	1 (0.89%)	1 (1.85%)
ALVEOLI	3 (2.67%)	1 (1.85%)
RECTUM	1 (0.89%)	0
SMALL BOWEL	1 (0.89%)	0
THYROID	2 (1.78%)	0
MULTIPLE MYELOMA	2 (1.78%)	0
GALLBLADDER	2 (1.78%)	0
METASTASIS OF UNKNOWN ORIGIN	1 (0.89%)	0
Co-Morbidities		
Diabetes	6 (5.35%)	0
Chemotherapy Regimen		
Taxanes	30 (26.78%)	6 (11.11%)
Platinum compounds	23 (20.53%)	24 (44.44%)
Bortezomib	1 (0.89%)	0
Combination chemotherapy	58 (51.78%)	24 (44.44%)

GENDER ANALYSIS :- A total study population of 166 patients has been assessed for the study. Among these population majority were of females constituting of 75% (n=125) and males of 25% (n=41).

TABLE :- 1

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	41	25.0
Female	125	75.0
Total	166	100.0

FIG NO : 1 Gender distribution in study population

AGE DISTRIBUTION:- According to the study in the study population the highest population were between ages of 41-50 years constituting of 36%(n=59) and lowest age group of age below 30 years constituting of 1% (n=2) and another respective age groups were mentioned below(table 2) .

TABLE :- 2

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 30 years	2	1.20
31-40 years	18	10.84
41-50 years	59	35.57
51-60 years	52	31.32

61-70 years	28	16.86
71-80 years	7	4.21
Total	166	100.0

FIG NO : 2 Age distribution in study population

AGE GENDER DISTRIBUTION:- According to the study the mean value of age gender distribution of the patients included in the study i.e upto 30 was of 2.00(n=2), 31-40 was of 9.00(n=18), 41-50 were of 29.5(n=59), 51-60 were of 26 (n=52), 61-70 were of 14 (n=28), 71-80 were of 3.5 (n=7)

TABLE :- 3

AGE	MALE	FEMALE	MEAN	SD	P VALUE
UPTO 30	2	0	2	1	
31-40	5	13	9	4	
41-50	4	55	29.5	25.5	

51-60	18	34	26	8	0.003366
61-70	9	19	14	5	
71-80	4	3	3.5	0.5	
Total	42	124	84	44	

FIG 3 :Age gender distribution among study population

DISEASE DISTRIBUTION:- According to the study there were various kinds of cancers involved in the study population as the greater extent were of the breast cancer patients constituting of 34%(n=57) and other types of cancers were mentioned below (table 4).

TABLE :- 4

S.no	Types of cancers	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1	Cancer of Breast	57	34
2	Cancer of lung	9	5
3	Cancer of cervix	23	14
4	Cancer of alveloi	1	1
5	Cancer of buccal mucosa	5	3
6	Cancer of endometrium	3	2
7	Cancer of epiglottis	1	1
8	Cancer of Gingiva	1	1
9	Cancer of hardpalate	2	1
10	Cancer of ovary	13	8
11	Cancer of hypopharynx	2	1
12	Cancer of larynx	2	1
13	Cancer of nasopharynx	1	1
14	Cancer of oropharynx	1	1
15	Cancer of pancreas	3	2
16	Cancer of penis	4	2
17	Cancer of post cricoid	4	2
18	Cancer of Rectosigmoid	3	2
19	Cancer of rectum	1	1

20	Cancer of Retromolar trigone	3	2
21	Cancer of small bowel	1	1
22	Cancer of stomach	6	4
23	Cancer of thyroid	2	1
24	Cancer of tongue	5	3
25	Cancer of upper esophagus	2	1
26	Cancer of vulva	1	1
27	Gastric cancer	2	1
28	Cancer of Gallbladder	2	1
29	Cancer of gastroesophageal junction	3	2
30	Multiple Myeloma	2	1
31	Cancer of MUO	1	1
	Total	166	100

FIG NO : 4 Types of cancers involved in study population

GRADE ANALYSIS:- According to the study in the study population there was an grading of 5 grades. Grade 1 constituting of 52% (n=87) & Grade 2 constituting of 14% (n= 24) whereas Grade 3 constituting of very less percentage of 1%(n=1), 33%(n=54) of study population exhibit no grading.

TABLE :- 5

Grades	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Grade 1	87	52
Grade 2	24	14
Grade 3	1	1
None	54	33
Total	166	100

FIG NO : 5 Analysis of grades of CIPN in study population

GRADING OF CHEMOTHERAPY INDUCED PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY

(CIPN) WITH DRUGS :- According to the study the incidence of CIPN with drugs in grading was mentioned below (table 6)

TABLE :- 6

Drugs	Grade – 1	Grade - 2	Grade -3
Paclitaxel	43	20	0
Cisplatin	22	1	0
Docetaxel	12	0	0
Oxaliplatin	8	3	0
Bortezomib	2	0	0
Carboplatin	0	0	1
Total	87	24	1

FIG NO : 6 Analysis of CIPN of drugs in study population

AGE WISE GRADING DISTRIBUTION:- According to the study the mean value of of the patients included in the study i.e upto 30 was of 0 (n=0), 31-40 was of 2.00(n=10), 41-50 were of 8.2(n=41), 51-60 were of 7.00 (n=35), 61-70 were of 4.00 (n=20), 71-80 were of 1.2 (n=6)

TABLE : 7

SI NO	AGE	GRADE 1	GRADE 2	GRADE 3	GRADE 4	GRADE 5	MEAN	SD	P VALUE
1	UPTO 30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002
2	31-40	8	2	0	0	0	2	3.0983	
3	41-50	34	7	0	0	0	8.2	13.181	
4	51-60	30	5	0	0	0	7	11.661	
5	61-70	12	7	1	0	0	4	4.3588	
6	71-80	3	3	0	0	0	1.2	1.4696	

FIG NO: 7 Age wise gender distribution among study population

GENDER WISE DRUGS DISTRIBUTION :- According to the study the mean value of gender wise drug distribution of the patients included in the study i.e males of 7.00(n=42) females of 20.66 (n=124)

TABLE :- 8

NO	Gender	Paclitaxel	Cisplatin	Docetaxel	Oxaliplatin	Carboplatin	Bortezomib	Mean	SD	P VALUE
1	MALE	15	16	3	7	0	1	7	6.403124	0.00427
2	FEMALE	59	31	22	9	2	1	20.6667	20.20451	

FIG NO : 8 Gender wise drug distribution among study population

INCIDENCE OF CHEMOTHERAPY INDUCED PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY(CIPN) OF DRUGS IN TOTAL STUDY POPULATION:-

According to the study the incidence of CIPN for the drugs among the study population was been analysed. The highest incidence is for paclitaxel constituting of 38%(n=63) and lowest incidence for carboplatin 0.60% (n=1) and the other drugs causing CIPN in the study population was mentioned below (table 9)

TABLE :- 9

DRUGS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Paclitaxel	63	38%
Cisplatin	23	14%
Docetaxel	12	7%
Oxaliplatin	11	7%
Bortezomib	2	1%
Carboplatin	1	0.60%

FIG NO : 9 Incidence of CIPN of drugs in study population**DISTRIBUTION OF CO –MORBIDITES:**

According to the study the co-morbidity of female was of 3.61%(n=6) and males of 0%(n=0)

TABLE :- 10

CO – MORBIDITES (Diabetes)	Frequency	Percentage
Male	0	0.00
Female	6	3.61
Total	6	3.61

FIG NO :10 Distribution of Co–morbidites in study population

CUMMULATIVE DOSE OF DRUGS :- According to the study the median cumulative doses of drugs paclitaxel having dose of (1050mg/m²), Oxaliplatin (780mg/m²), Docetaxel (450mg/m²), Cisplatin (240mg/m²), Carboplatin (900mg/m²) Bortezomib (7.8mg/m²).

DRUG	MEDIAN CUMMULATIVE DOSE
Paclitaxel	1050 mg/m ²
Oxaliplatin	780 mg/m ²
Docetaxel	450 mg/m ²
Cisplatin	240 mg/m ²
Carboplatin	900 mg/m ²
Bortezomib	7.8 mg/m ²

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the incidence and associated risk factors of chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) among oncology patients receiving various chemotherapeutic agents. Our findings reveal that **37% of patients developed symptoms of CIPN**, with the highest incidence observed in those treated with **paclitaxel** and **oxaliplatin**—consistent with existing literature identifying these agents as highly neurotoxic [Awad & Voruganti, 2008; Seretny et al., 2014].

The majority of patients developed **sensory neuropathy**, including numbness, tingling, and burning sensations, particularly in the hands and feet. A smaller proportion experienced **motor symptoms** such as muscle weakness, and **autonomic symptoms** like orthostatic hypotension. These patterns are consistent with prior studies that suggest sensory nerves are most vulnerable to chemotherapy-induced damage due to their long axons and limited regenerative capacity.

Our results indicate that **older age, higher cumulative doses, and pre-existing conditions** such as diabetes mellitus were significantly associated with increased risk of CIPN. These findings align with previous studies that have identified similar risk factors [Park et al., 2013; Flatters et al., 2017]. The cumulative neurotoxic effect of chemotherapy appears to be dose-dependent, underscoring the importance of monitoring and possibly adjusting doses in vulnerable populations.

An important finding in this study is the **under-recognition of CIPN** by healthcare providers during routine treatment monitoring. Despite the high incidence, a notable proportion of patients reported inadequate symptom management, suggesting a need for standardized assessment tools to routinely evaluate and document CIPN.

The **impact of CIPN on quality of life** cannot be overstated. Many patients reported difficulty with activities of daily living, impaired mobility, and psychological distress. These effects may lead to **dose reduction or discontinuation of chemotherapy**, ultimately affecting treatment efficacy and long-term outcomes.

CONCLUSION

- Compared with platinum compounds in chemotherapy anti-microtubule agents showed a significant result in patients undergoing chemotherapy that causing peripheral neuropathy.
- Compared with peripheral motor neuropathy in the study peripheral sensory neuropathy showed a greater range of incidence in the study population.
- There was a less significance of co-morbidities of (1%) does not show any variation of inducing peripheral neuropathy.
- The median cumulative dose of various drugs has been calculated as per the chemotherapy cycles and there was greater significance of neuropathy was shown with anti-microtubule agents.
- There was a dose reduction has been done for every patient consisting of grade -2 of neuropathy in the study population.

The major findings in our study includes:

- In our study population females are more compared to males out of 166 sample size.
- In our study, the incidence of CIPN was **67.46%**.
- In our study population most of the patients presented with **52%** (n=87) grade I CIPN, **14%** (n=24) grade II, and **1%** (n=1) developed grade III CIPN.
- No comorbidity was statistically significantly associated with a higher risk of CIPN in our study.

- The highest incidence of CIPN was associated with paclitaxel **38%** (n=63), and with cisplatin**14%** (n=23), followed by oxaliplatin **7%** (n=11), and with docetaxel **7%** (n=2).
- We also observed that for paclitaxel a median cumulative dose of **1050 mg/m²** was associated with a higher incidence of CIPN.
- Carboplatin is less neurotoxic comparing with cisplatin or oxaliplatin, **0.60%** of patients receiving carboplatin may develop neuropathy.
- No clinical significant difference was found in our study regarding the patients receiving single agent regimen or combination of chemotherapeutic drugs, regarding the severity of CIPN.

This study also sought to explore how comorbidities effects the quality of life. Duration of untreated illness had no impact on worsening of quality of life, because once the treatment begins, the disease condition gets better.

MEASURES TO IMPROVE PATIENT QUALITY OF LIFE:

- Chemotherapy induced peripheral neuropathy is always associated with dose. So if any patient experience neuropathy i.e., paresthesia, dyesthesia etc, immediately informed to the doctor. So the doctor either can reduce the dose of the drug according to patient condition or prescribe the alternative medicine (drugs that reduce the neuropathic pain eg: gabapentin.)
- Caregivers should focus on incorporating foods with anti-inflammatory properties into a balanced diet. These foods include whole grains, lean meats such as poultry and fish are high in vitamin B12, which helps to keep blood cells and nerves healthy.
- Massage improves blood flow and may offer temporary relief from symptoms. Some people may tense their muscles in response to neuropathic pain and massage can help release this tension, which may prevent the pain from radiating.
- **Safety tips :-**
 - Be extra cautious with sharp objects.
 - Inspect your fingers and feet regularly for cuts and scrapes.
 - Avoid walking on uneven surfaces.

- Consider handrails in stairways
- Keep dark areas well lighted and use a night light as needed.
- For leg and/or foot neuropathy, patients should try calf stretches, ankle circles, gentle walking, leg lifts, and balancing exercises.
- If the neuropathy is in your feet, sit down as much as possible, even while brushing your teeth or cooking.
- For neuropathy in the hands, patients can try finger taps (tap each finger to the thumb, one at a time) or finger rolls (bend fingers, one at a time, into a fist).
- If you have neuropathy in your hands, be very careful when using knives, scissors, box cutters, and other sharp objects. Use them only when you can give your full attention to your task.
- If you need one, use a cane, walker or wheelchair.
- Let people help you with difficult tasks. Slow down and give yourself more time to do things.
- Acupuncture, relaxation techniques, meditation, and guided imagery exercises can all help with the side effects of neuropathy.
- Protect yourself from heat injuries. Neuropathy would be associated with sensory loss as this leads to injuries caused by heat.
- Before touching water with your hands or feet, feel the water with a part of your body such as the underside of your forearm that can sense how warm it is. And, avoid using heating pads and hot water bottles.

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